

Characterization of the essential oil of *Mucuna pruriens* (L.) leaves cultivated in Bulgaria

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Abstract

Mucuna pruriens (L.) DC, a member of the Fabaceae family, represents one of the most extensively studied species within the genus *Mucuna*. It is an annual, tropical, leguminous medicinal plant widely utilized in traditional Ayurvedic medicine throughout Asia and Africa. Globally, it is recognized as a plant employed in the management of Parkinson's disease. It is also valued for its aphrodisiac, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and fertility-enhancing properties. The aim of the present study was to investigate the biological variability in the composition of the essential oil obtained from the less-studied leaves of *M. pruriens* cultivated and harvested outside its native habitat. For this purpose, hydrodistillation was performed using a Clevenger-type apparatus, yielding a light yellowish liquid, which was collected and analyzed using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS). A total of 20 volatile compounds were identified, representing 89.80% of the total oil composition. The predominant constituents comprised carotenoid derivatives (34.89%), utilized for their antioxidant, vision-supporting, and immune-stimulating properties. The obtained results demonstrate that *M. pruriens* cultivated under Bulgarian environmental conditions retains the capacity to synthesize a diverse array of biologically active volatile compounds, some of which differ from those previously reported in plants grown within their native habitat.

Keywords

Antioxidant, carotenoids, essential oil, GC–MS, hydrodistillation, *Mucuna pruriens*, Parkinson's disease

Introduction

Mucuna pruriens (L.) DC. is an annual, diploid, tropical legume species belonging to the family Fabaceae. It is a climbing legume distributed across Africa and Asia. This species is a well-recognized Ayurvedic medicinal plant, commonly known as velvet bean or cowhage (Lampariello et al. 2012; Rai et al. 2017). The plant is characterized by its elongated, slender stems and alternately arranged,

lanceolate leaves. It bears white flowers with a bluish-purple hue, resembling butterflies. Its seed pods are robust and leathery, typically measuring around 10 cm in length. These pods, reminiscent of violin f-holes, are densely covered with coarse, stiff hairs and usually contain four to six dark brown seeds (Gulati et al. 2012; Dendup et al. 2014). The golden-brown hairs are toxic due to the presence of serotonin, causing itching upon contact (Rai et al. 2017). The chemical composition of *M. pruriens* varies

considerably depending on the plant organ analyzed. The species contains a wide range of secondary metabolites, including alkaloids such as prurienine, prurieninine, and prurienidine (Misra and Wagner 2004), as well as triterpenoids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic acids, and cardiac glycosides. It is particularly notable for its high content (4–5%) of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-DOPA) (Lieu et al. 2012; Suresh et al. 2013; Rai et al. 2017). Moreover, *M. pruriens* is used as a food source due to its high protein content and is rich in essential nutrients, including amino acids, micro- and macronutrients, fatty acids, and carbohydrates, which make it a valuable crop (Carew and Gernat 2006; Rai et al. 2017). It has been reported that the leaves of *M. pruriens* are rich in essential oil (EO), predominantly comprising linalool and trans-dehydroxylinalool oxide. It has been associated with notable pro-inflammatory activity (Avoseh et al. 2020; Gvozdeva and Georgieva 2025). In Ayurvedic medicine, the seeds of *M. pruriens* have traditionally been used for their anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties (Rai et al. 2017). It has been suggested that *M. pruriens* may provide advantages over conventional L-DOPA preparations in the long-term management of Parkinson's disease. Furthermore, studies have indicated that the plant species may exert immunomodulatory effects, which could contribute to its therapeutic potential (Rai et al. 2017; Yotov et al. 2023). Owing to its variety of bioactive compounds, *M. pruriens* exhibits a wide range of pharmacological properties, including antitumor, antivenom, antidiabetic, aphrodisiac, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activities (Kokova and Apostolova 2023; Chookiat et al. 2024; Gvozdeva et al. 2025). Consequently, the plant has been incorporated into numerous phytotherapeutic formulations worldwide, particularly for the treatment of infertility (Eze and Ndukwe 2012; Obogwu et al. 2014; Sahoo et al. 2014; Ardasheva et al. 2024; Rajpoot et al. 2025).

Although extensive research has been conducted on the seeds and other plant parts of *M. pruriens*, data concerning the EO derived from its leaves remain limited. Therefore, the objective of this research was to evaluate the chemical composition of the EO isolated from the leaves of *M. pruriens* cultivated in Bulgaria, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of this medicinally significant species.

Materials and methods

Plant material and oil extraction

Mucuna pruriens (L.) DC was cultivated in the Krumovgrad region, located in the floristic zone of the Rhodope Mountains, Bulgaria (41.465694, 25.671072). The leaves were harvested and air-dried under laboratory shade for 2 weeks at 24 °C to reduce moisture content. The dried leaves (100 g) were chopped and subjected to hydrodistillation using a Clevenger-type apparatus for 4 hours. The obtained EO was dried over anhydrous sodium

sulfate and stored in brown vials at 4 °C until further analysis. The EO yield (0.1%) was calculated as the percentage (v/w) of oil obtained from the dry plant material.

Chemicals and reagents

The hydrocarbons used for the determination of retention indices (RIs)—decane (≥99%), undecane (≥99%), dodecane (99%), tridecane (≥99%), tetradecane (≥99%), and hexadecane (≥99%)—were purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). Hexane (GC-MS grade) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH (Bremen, Germany).

Chromatographic conditions

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) was employed for the analysis, utilizing a Bruker Scion 436-GC SQ MS system (Bremen, Germany). The separation was performed on a Bruker BR-5 ms fused silica capillary column with dimensions of 30 m × 0.25 mm internal diameter and a film thickness of 0.25 µm. The oven temperature was initially held at 70 °C for 1 min, then increased to 150 °C at a rate of 3 °C/min, and subsequently increased to 210 °C at 10 °C/min and held for 1 min. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injector split ratio was 1:5, with an injection volume of 1 µL. The range of m/z was 50–350 in the full-scan mode. Spectral data and retention indices were compared using the Wiley NIST11 Mass Spectral Library (NIST11/2011/EPA/NIH), Adams' compendium of retention indices, and literature data. Retention index values were calculated and verified against reported values for a C₁₀–C₁₆ series of *n*-alkane standards (Linstrom 1997; Adams 2007).

Results and discussion

The EO obtained from *M. pruriens* leaves was characterized by an intense fragrance and a light-yellowish coloration. Representative chromatograms of *M. pruriens* leaf EO are presented in Fig. 1, while the identified chemical compounds are summarized in Table 1.

A total of 20 volatile constituents were tentatively identified in *M. pruriens* EO cultivated in Bulgaria, representing 89.80% of the total oil composition. These compounds were classified into six major groups: monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, carotenoid derivatives, aromatic aldehydes, and other oxygenated compounds. The EO was characterized by a marked predominance of oxygenated compounds, which accounted for 86.36% of the total composition, while non-oxygenated compounds constituted only 3.44%. The principal constituents of the EO were (+)-3-carene, 10-(acetylmethyl) (24.91%), dihydro-β-ionone (19.25%), β-damascenone (8.95%), and phytol (6.23%). Carotenoid derivatives (apocarotenoids) formed the most abundant chemical class (34.89%), with dihydro-β-ionone, β-damascenone, and β-ionone epoxide as the principal representatives. Oxygenated monoterpenes

Figure 1. GC–MS chromatogram of *M. pruriens* EO from leaves, where major peaks correspond to: **1.** 3-Carene,10-(acetylmethyl), **2.** Dihydro-β-ionone, **3.** β-Damascenone.

Table 1. Percentage chemical composition of *M. pruriens* EO.

Nº	Compound	Molecular formula	RI	% of Total
1.	Benzaldehyde	C ₇ H ₆ O	988	3.29
2.	2- <i>n</i> -Pentylfuran	C ₉ H ₁₄ O	1005	1.18
3.	<i>cis</i> -2-(2-Pentenyl) furan	C ₉ H ₁₂ O	1010	1.63
4.	<i>trans</i> , <i>trans</i> -2,4-Heptadienal	C ₇ H ₁₀ O	1020	0.24
5.	2,2,6-Trimethylcyclohexanone	C ₉ H ₁₆ O	1038	0.32
6.	Benzene acetaldehyde	C ₈ H ₈ O	1045	3.24
7.	Linalool	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	1093	1.43
8.	Pelargonaldehyde	C ₉ H ₁₈ O	1097	1.78
9.	L-Camphor	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	1138	1.17
10.	3-Ethylbenzaldehyde	C ₉ H ₁₀ O	1153	0.55
11.	Safranal	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O	1189	1.84
12.	β-Cyclocitral	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	1209	2.40
13.	α-Longipinene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	1325	3.44
14.	β-Damascenone	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O	1376	8.95
15.	3-Carene, 10-(acetylmethyl)	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O	1385	24.91
16.	Dihydro-β-ionone	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O	1410	19.25
17.	β-Ionone	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O	1442	0.85
18.	<i>trans</i> -Geranylacetone	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ O	1448	0.64
19.	β-Ionone epoxide	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₂	1478	5.59
20.	Phytol	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	2134	6.23
	Total identified (%)			89.80
	Total non-oxygenated compounds			3.44
	Total oxygenated compounds			86.36

* The data represent the mean of three independent samples. The standard error of the mean does not exceed 2% and was therefore omitted for clarity.

comprised about 8.84% of the total composition, represented by linalool (1.43%), L-camphor (1.17%), safranal (1.84%), and β-cyclocitral (2.40%). Aromatic aldehydes contributed approximately 7.08%, including benzaldehyde (3.29%), benzene acetaldehyde (3.24%), and 3-ethylbenzaldehyde (0.55%). Minor fractions included furan deriva-

tives (2.81%), sesquiterpenes (α-longipinene, 3.44%), and diterpenes (phytol, 6.23%). The relatively high proportions of 3-carene, 10-(acetylmethyl), and dihydro-β-ionone suggest a unique chemotype, potentially associated with the environmental and geographical conditions of cultivation, which may contribute to the characteristic aroma and bioactivity of the EO. Comparable amounts of oxygenated monoterpenes were reported (10.8% in the Nigerian sample vs. 8.95% in the Bulgarian sample), as well as sesquiterpenes (1.8% vs. 3.24%, respectively). Notably, the diterpene content in the Bulgarian EO was nearly twice as high (Avoseh et al. 2020). The chemical composition of the EO is influenced by various factors such as climate, geographical latitude, solar exposure, genetic traits, and extraction methodology. Variations in composition may also occur depending on which part of the plant is utilized. Studies on the chemical composition of *M. pruriens* leaf EO obtained through hydrodistillation remain limited. For instance, a study conducted in Nigeria identified 36 constituents, with (*E*)-2-hexenal, linalool, and 1-hexanol as the major compounds. In that research, non-terpenes represented the predominant class of compounds, in contrast to the present findings, where a class of carotenoid oxidation products was found to be dominant. Comparable amounts of oxygenated monoterpenes were reported (10.8% in the Nigerian sample vs. 8.95% in the Bulgarian sample), as well as sesquiterpenes (1.8% vs. 3.24%, respectively). Notably, the diterpene content was approximately twice as high in the Bulgarian EO (Avoseh et al. 2020).

Previously, it has been reported that EO containing 3-carene, 10-(acetylmethyl) exhibits potent antibacterial activity (Aghoutane et al. 2020; Politeo et al. 2024). Moreover, safranal has been reported to exhibit pronounced antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and gastroprotective properties (Esmailzadeh et al. 2023). Likewise, longipinene and linalool are recognized for their antibacterial and antifungal activities (Manoharan et al. 2017). In addition,

Table 2. Comparison of the main volatile constituents of the EO of *M. pruriens* L. from different geographical regions.

Plant collecting region	Plant materials	Number of identified compounds	Main volatile compounds	Ref.
Bulgaria	Leaves	Twenty volatile constituents were tentatively identified in the essential oil of <i>M. pruriens</i> cultivated in Bulgaria, accounting for 89.80% of the total oil composition.	(+)-3-carene, 10-(acetylmethyl) (24.91%), dihydro- β -ionone (19.25%), β -damascenone (8.95%), phytol (6.23%).	Present study
Imota, Ikorodu Forest Reserve, Lagos State, Nigeria	Leaves	Thirty-six compounds were identified, accounting for 94.8% of the EO composition.	(<i>E</i>)-2-hexenal (19.0%), linalool (8.9%), 1-hexanol (6.6%), trans-dehydroxylinalool oxide (5.2%)	(Avoseh et al. 2020)
Not reported	Seeds	Five compounds were reported.	Hydroxylamine (88%), phthalic acid, butyl hept-3-yl e (11%)	(Arasu et al. 2019)

dehydro- β -ionone and nonanal are metabolites associated with the plant's defensive response to environmental stress (Brambilla et al. 2022). Therefore, the presence of these bioactive constituents may substantially contribute to the overall biological potential of the EO, particularly in terms of its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects.

Studies investigating the chemical profiles of *M. pruriens* EOs remain limited. The main volatile constituents and the number of identified compounds reported in these studies are summarized in Table 2.

Although Table 2 provides a general comparison of the reported volatile constituents of *M. pruriens* EOs from different geographical regions, direct conclusions remain difficult. The available studies analyze different plant organs and were conducted under varying environmental conditions and extraction methodologies, which can markedly affect the composition of the EO. Consequently, the observed differences likely reflect both biological variability and methodological factors rather than strict chemotypic distinctions.

Variations in the chemical composition of *Mucuna* EOs may be related to differences in cultivation practices and geographical origin, which can influence the accumulation of secondary metabolites in plants. Environmental factors such as light intensity and soil characteristics, including pH and mineral composition, may also affect the biosynthesis and accumulation of volatile compounds. In addition, climatic conditions play an important role in determining EO composition, such as temperature and the flowering stage (Barra 2009; Hassiotis et al. 2014; Gruda et al. 2019; Todorova et al. 2023).

The plant samples investigated in this study were collected from the Eastern Rhodope Mountains in Bulgaria, a region influenced by a transitional climate combining both continental and Mediterranean characteristics. The soils in this area are commonly associated with serpentine geological formations and typically exhibit a neutral to slightly alkaline pH. These soils are generally characterized by moderate to relatively high organic matter content and support a rich and diverse plant community, including several specialized and endemic taxa. Such environmental and edaphic conditions may affect the biosynthesis and accumulation of secondary metabolites in plants and could therefore contribute to the specific chemical profile observed in the essential oil of the analyzed material.

Conclusion

The successful extraction of EO from *M. pruriens* leaves in the present study demonstrates the considerable biological diversity of the plant's secondary metabolites. Cultivation outside its native tropical habitat did not hinder its growth. On the contrary, it appeared to enhance the biosynthetic potential for the production of biologically active compounds, including 3-carene, 10-(acetylmethyl), dihydro- β -ionone, and β -damascenone. These findings provide valuable insights into the chemical composition and potential applications of *M. pruriens* EO. The results also highlight the remarkable adaptability of this species to non-native environmental conditions and its ability to maintain or even increase the production of pharmacologically relevant metabolites. Overall, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the phytochemical profile and biological potential of *M. pruriens* cultivated outside its natural distribution range and expands the currently limited knowledge regarding the EO composition of *M. pruriens* leaves.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, Z.B., D.K.-B., and S.I.; methodology, Z.B., D.K.-B., V.T., and S.I.; formal analysis, Z.B., D.K.-B., V.T., and R.A.; investigation, Z.B., D.K.-B., V.T., R.A., and S.I.; resources, Z.B.; data curation, Z.B., D.K.-B., V.T., R.A., and K.I.; writing – original draft preparation, Z.B., D.K.-B., V.T., R.A., and S.I.; writing – review and editing, D.K.-B., V.T., K.I., and S.I.; visual-

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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